

Method B¹⁵: The thiosemicarbazide (3; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in methanol and mercuric oxide (0.011 mol) was added to it. The contents were refluxed for 2–4 h and then filtered hot. The filtrate thus obtained was evaporated and the resulting solid recrystallised from dilute alcohol; other compounds of the series were prepared similarly (Table 1) (Found: C, 54.52; N, 13.60. C₁₄H₉N₃OCl calcd. for: C, 54.90 N, 13.72%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 150–3 390 (NH), 1 610 (C=N) and 1 250–1 270 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); δ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 6.50–8.00 (9H, m, Ar–H and NH).

2-Substituted-amino-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole¹⁶ (5a): The thiosemicarbazide (3a; 3.40 g, 0.01 mol) was added gradually with stirring during 20 min to syrupy phosphoric acid (85%, 25 ml) at 120°. The mixture was heated under stirring at that temperature for further 30 min and then poured into ice-water (500 ml) and left overnight. The precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol (95%, charcoal) to afford 5a; all the thiadiazole derivatives thus prepared are listed in Table 1 (Found: C, 52.32; N, 12.50. C₁₄H₉N₃SCl₂ calcd. for: C, 52.17; N, 13.04%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 175–3 320 (NH) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 6.6–8.2 (9H, m, Ar–H and NH).

Fungitoxic activity: The synthesised compounds were screened for their fungitoxic properties using the method of Horsfall and Rich¹⁷ on two test organisms, *Curvularia verruciformis* and *Alternaria tenuis*. The percentage of conidial inhibition was calculated by comparing the percentage germination of treated slides with the control. Average results of four replications are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PERCENTAGE INHIBITION OF CONIDIAL GERMINATION IN TEST SOLUTIONS

Compd. no.	% Inhibition*	
	<i>C. verruciformis</i>	<i>A. tenuis</i>
4a	+	—
4b	—	—
4c	—	—
4d	—	—
4e	—	—
4f	—	—
4g	—	—
5a	+	+
5b	+	—
5c	++++	+++
5d	+	—
5e	+	+
5f	—	—
5g	—	—
5h	+	+

* (—) = No inhibition, (+) = 0–25%, (++) = 25–50%, (+++) = 51–75%, and (++++) = 76–100% inhibition.

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Partial Amino Terminal Sequence of Globulin from *Phaseolus vulgaris*, *Vigna mungo* and *Vigna radiata*

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A variety of beans is cultivated throughout India and constitute a major dietary protein source for vegetarian population. Several workers^{1–4} have reported the isolation of major storage protein from *Phaseolus vulgaris* consisting of glycoproteins and globulins of high molecular weight containing bound carbohydrate. Recently, we isolated⁵ pure homogeneous major protein globulin from three edible beans, viz. *P. vulgaris* Linn. (french beans), *Vigna mungo* Linn. (black gram) and *V. radiata* Linn. (green gram) using gel filtration and electrophoresis followed by determination of amino acid composition of each protein using standard methods of chromatography⁶ and spectrophotometry^{7,8}. Present communication reports the NH₂-terminal Edman degradation and partial sequence of each protein.

Literature reveals that no similar work on these proteins has been reported.

Experimental

The beans were purchased from the local market (1983 harvest). Reagents used were of A.R. grade. Colorimetric measurements were made by a ECIL GS66B spectrophotometer and uv spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss Specord UV-VIS apparatus.

The proteins from the three beans were isolated, purified and homogeneity was ascertained by PAGE⁹ and as reported in our earlier work^{5,10}. The electrophoresis⁹ was carried out in the pH range 3–9 using acetate, tris-glycine and tris-borate buffers under varying voltage of 400–500 V and time 3–6 h. The protein content was determined spectrophotometrically¹¹ and molecular weights were determined by gel filtrations¹². The proteins were subjected to Manual-Edman degradation^{13–16} by dissolving each protein (200 nmol) in aqueous dioxane (50%, 6 ml) and treating with phenyl isothiocyanate (0.1 ml) at the pH 9. The solution was stirred for 1.5 h at 40°, extracted several times with benzene and concentrated to dryness in vacuum over NaOH. The sodium salt was redissolved in water and acidified with 6N HCl. The PTH-amino acid was extracted with ethyl acetate, and the residue recovered by concentrating the aqueous solution was submitted to the same cycle of operations. Thus, seven sequential residues for each protein were separated. PTH-amino acids were identified by tlc¹⁷ and uv¹⁸. Tlc was carried¹⁷ out on silica plates (0.5 mm × 20 × 20 cm) using hexane-n-butanol (3 : 2, v/v) and benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 1, v/v) as the developing solvents and the spots were located in iodine chamber. Uv spectra were recorded in ethanol (1 × 10⁻⁴ M) and molar extinction coefficients calculated¹⁹ at 245 and 269 nm. The ratio $\epsilon_{245}/\epsilon_{269}$ was calculated and served as a sensitive criterion for the purity of products¹⁹. The R_f values and $\epsilon_{245}/\epsilon_{269}$ of the unknown PTH-amino acids were in good agreement with those of the standard PTH-amino acids prepared²⁰ for this purpose.

The globulin 100 fraction was the primary source of the major bean protein and accounts for about 40% of the total. The molecular weight was found to be about 1,86,000. Partial amino acid sequence of the globulins as determined by Edman method are as follows: *P. vulgaris*, Arg-Val-Phe-Lys-Gly-Ala-Met-; *V. mungo*, Phe-Glu-Lys-Val-Pro-Arg-Leu-; *V. radiata*, Gly-Val-Val-Cys-Lys-Leu-Ile-. The readily accessible amino-terminal sequences of proteins have been of interest in several fields. The study of the amino-terminal sequences of nascent polypeptide has demonstrated that many proteins excreted from cells are synthesised as precursors. Further, amino-terminal partial sequences can be correlated with nucleotide sequences determined from cloned cDNA or genomic DNA.

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Copper with Bromopyrogallol Red and Benzyldimethylphenylammonium Chloride

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BROMOPYROGALLOL red in presence of long-chain quaternary ammonium salts, viz. cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide, benzyldimethyltetradecylammonium chloride and tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide has been in use in the spectrophotometric determination of some metal ions¹⁻⁶. In this paper, we present a method for extractive spectrophotometric determination of copper in micro quantities using bromopyrogallol red (BPR) and benzyldimethylphenylammonium chloride (BDPA-